

Does policy uncertainty affect landowners' willingness to engage in afforestation schemes? – A stated preference study among Danish landowners

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Does policy uncertainty affect landowners' willingness to engage in afforestation schemes? – A stated preference study among Danish landowners

Voluntary subsidy schemes are widely used to reach national and supranational environmental goals. In Denmark a policy objective of increasing the forest cover by 38% in 20 years, primarily through voluntary schemes, highlights the importance of understanding landowners' decision making. In this context, afforestation entails a statutory prohibition against any future land-use change. This may be a barrier, as the future is uncertain and we don't know which land-uses will become more attractive. Despite many studies investigating preferences for contract designs for agri-environmental schemes, few address the option value related to permanent land use changes. We use a choice experiment with a split design, to investigate the size of such an option value among Danish landowners. We find that the compensation needed estimated as willingness to accept (WTA) for entering an afforestation contract generally is higher than the opportunity cost of such afforestation. A large share of this can be explained by the option value which accounts for 21-66% of the compensation. Hence, reducing policy uncertainty can reduce the WTA. We also find that property size and required enrollment size matter, leading to higher per hectare compensation for large landowners and large land areas.

Keywords: Agri-environmental schemes, Forestry, Land use change, Option values, Policy uncertainty

Key policy highlights:

- Increasing certainty of changes in subsidy levels could potentially decrease the required subsidies needed to get landowners to join.

- On average, landowners with 50 ha or more, of agricultural land, require higher per hectare compensation to join afforestation schemes than landowners with less than 50 ha.
- There is an increasing marginal compensation requirement. This means that large coherent nature areas require substantially higher per hectare subsidy levels than small areas.

1. Introduction

Politically desired land use changes can be incentivized through voluntary subsidy schemes. Around EU a range of agri-environmental schemes, designed as voluntary subsidy schemes, have been introduced to incentivize landowners to change to less intensive land uses. Despite the good intentions with voluntary schemes, it is seen that several of these schemes have had limited effects due to their voluntary nature and lack of landowner participation (Lienhoop and Brouwer 2015; Christensen et al. 2011; Espinosa-Goded, Barreiro-Hurlé, and Ruto 2010). Landowner participation in agri-environmental schemes has been discussed in academic papers for many years, mainly with a focus on design and implementation (Raina et al. 2021). Ambitious environmental policies, putting pressure on land use for mutually exclusive purposes can cause the voluntary schemes to change over time. The nature of the schemes and the changes they potentially undertake depend on political priorities, and how successful the governments are in reaching certain political goals. Changes in the schemes can be a de- or increase of compensation levels over time depending on policy success, or the schemes are likely to change or be replaced by other schemes. For landowners, who are to decide whether to join such schemes or not, this imposes uncertainty about future possibilities for their land. If there is uncertainty about the future options, this may be even more pronounced. Thus, landowners may be reluctant to enter contracts with permanence requirements – as they want to wait for possible better options. This is the topic of the current paper – taking point of departure in the case of afforestation subsidies in Denmark.

Denmark currently has various environmental schemes for farmland areas, including afforestation schemes, that landowners can participate in (Landbrugsstyrelsen 2025). Most of these are schemes with conditions that last for a limited period, but afforestation schemes restrict future land use conversion (SGARV 2025). Over the last two centuries, there has been a political ambition to increase the forest area in Denmark, which has resulted in a net increase of forest since 1881 (Nord-Larsen et al. 2025). From 2018 to 2023 the forest cover increased with 4,900 ha per year, largely driven by afforestation on private agricultural land, leading to a total forest cover in Denmark of 651,757 ha by the end of 2023, taking up approximately 15.1% of the Danish land area (Nord-Larsen et al. 2025). In 2024 a major political agreement was settled, primarily aiming at reducing greenhouse gas and nitrate emissions from agriculture. One sub-target of the agreement is to establish 250,000 ha new forest in Denmark before 2045, with the majority driven

by voluntary land-use change on private agricultural land (The Danish Government 2024). This corresponds to an expected 38% increase in forest cover from 2024 - 2045. Hence, understanding private landowners' drivers and barriers towards afforestation schemes is important if the goal is to be reached. Landowners' incentives and behavior regarding land-use change have previously been studied in relation to changing to more extensive agricultural practices (Thompson et al. 2024; Swart et al. 2023; Hasler et al. 2019; Raina et al. 2021; Greiner 2016; Christensen et al. 2011; Latacz-Lohmann, Schulz, and Breustedt 2014; Espinosa-Goded, Barreiro-Hurlé, and Ruto 2010; Dessart, Barreiro-Hurlé, and Van Bavel 2019), setting aside agricultural land for peatland restoration and conservation, doing afforestation or changing forest management practices to reach recreational or environmental goals (Vesterlund et al. 2023; Broch et al. 2013; Nielsen et al. 2017; Boon, Meilby, and Thorsen 2004; Lienhoop and Brouwer 2015). Swart et al. (2023) found, based on a literature review, that landowners in Europe are not only motivated by profitability, but also their attitude and intention matter as well as the landowner's perceived usefulness of the environmental measure. In line with this, Boon et al. (2004) found that Danish forest owners can be divided into three groups with different incentives for managing their forest, with the first group being highly driven by economic motives, the second group more driven by own recreational interests and the last group not having a specific characteristic but in general being more indifferent about the management of their forest.

Several studies have employed stated preference methods to investigate the motivations and barriers for afforestation schemes (Vedel, Jacobsen, and Thorsen 2015; Broch and Vedel 2012; Raina et al. 2021; Weller and Elsasser 2018; Lienhoop and Brouwer 2015). These studies have primarily focused on investigating landowners' utility or disutility for various attributes. Examples of this can be the utility of wood production, the option to cancel the contracts or the subsidy level, or the disutility of monitoring, restrictions in contracts, duration lengths or the lost income from alternative land-use, typically agriculture. One aspect has drawn particular attention in the literature, namely that when entering a contract of a permanent land use change, the landowner loses the option to convert to another land-use. As the world is uncertain, this could imply a significant loss. When the future is uncertain and decisions are irreversible, the possibility of revealing outcomes in the future possess a value. This value of waiting (for the uncertainty to be revealed) is called a real option value (Dixit and Pindyck 1994). The notion option value,

will in this paper be used when referring to the value of waiting. The importance of such option values has been investigated theoretically and empirically and has been the topic of previous investigations related to land-use change (Arrow and Fisher 1974; Thorsen 1999; Abildtrup and Strange 1999; Broch and Vedel 2012). For example, Thorsen (1999), investigates the real option value of afforestation with a focus on the uncertain profitability of afforestation, and Abildtrup and Strange (1999) investigate the option value of non-contaminated forest watersheds. Empirically, Broch & Vedel (2012) find that offering farmers who are to enter an afforestation scheme, a regret option, lowers the compensation they require. They propose the reason to be the unfamiliarity that a typical farmer has with forestry, and hence the possibility that if they gain more insight in the future, this could remove some of the uncertainty. More broadly, uncertainty can be related to the knowledge of the individual decision maker (Broch & Vedel, 2012) or the market uncertainty as such (Thorsen, 1999).

A different kind of uncertainty relates to political uncertainty; how will governments change the subsidies in the future? In Europe, the common agricultural policy (CAP) is currently under revision. The Danish political agreement on afforestation is ambitious and has a specific goal (Jensen 2024). Will governments change the designed incentives to reach the goal if they see that the current ones will not fulfill the target? In the ongoing public debate, this political uncertainty is raised as a reason for landowners holding back on land-use change (Bisgaard 2024; Hansen 2023). These questions are studied little in the scientific literature and hence, the motivation of the current paper is to explore the importance of this.

In this study, we therefore focus on the uncertainty that emerges from political ambitious goals involving land-use change on private land, leading to uncertainty about future possibilities when decisions are irreversible caused by afforestation schemes having permanence restrictions. We investigate the option value by attempting to eliminate some of the short-term uncertainty concerning changes in the afforestation schemes. This is done by carrying out a choice experiment with a split design, where three groups of respondents, are faced with different splits, 1) a neutral scenario: no information about uncertainties of future schemes is provided, 2) an information scenario: we highlight that that future schemes might offer better or worse payments than the ones available now depending on progress towards 2030, 3) an uncertainty reduction scenario: the same information as in the second split is provided, but a premium is introduced to cover policy

uncertainty: if a contract is accepted and policy changes lead to a positive increase in future subsidy level within the first five years, the difference will be covered. Comparing the third split with the first two splits allows us to test whether removing the policy uncertainty affects landowners' willingness to participate. The option value and the mechanism which is introduced is only related to the uncertainty that emerges from policy changes. Any uncertainty related to e.g. future agricultural income remains.

Based on this, the core hypothesis is:

- 1) Respondents will have a higher willingness to enter a contract if they get compensated for a potential increase in future subsidy levels than if not.

The core hypothesis reflects a disutility of policy uncertainty. The size of the estimate can potentially be used by policymakers to design contracts that incentivize landowners to enroll and afforest land faster than otherwise. If the hypothesis is not rejected, we can compare the estimates for the three splits to find an option value, describing the value of reducing the uncertainty of future subsidy levels. We triangulate the results by comparing with opportunity cost estimates.

Alongside answering the core hypothesis, we will also investigate the following underlying hypotheses;

- 1.1 Respondents' willingness to enter contracts is independent of the information on uncertainty related to future schemes.
- 1.2 Landowners' willingness to enter an afforestation scheme is affected by their property size.

Hypothesis 1.1 reflects that we would expect respondents to be aware of policy uncertainty, even if not informed of it. Hence results for split one and two should be identical under this hypothesis. However, information is often found to affect preferences (Brahic and Rambonilaza 2015). So, to be able to distinguish a potential information effect from the uncertainty reducing effect in split 3, we need to test this.

Hypothesis 1.2 reflects that in a case where Denmark must increase their forest area with 38% in 20 years, it is necessary to include different types of landowners with different property sizes. Previous literature on Danish landowners have shown conflicting results in whether property-size effects the decision making (Lautrup et al. 2023; Broch and Vedel 2012) and we therefore find it interesting to get a better understanding of this.

In the remaining of this paper, we will in section 2 explain the concept of option values in the specific afforestation case, followed by section 3 with a description of the data

used for estimating it. Section 4 describes the method, and in section 5 we present the results. Section 6 and 7 discusses and concludes on the results and policy implications.

2. Deriving option values

We assume a utility maximizing landowner who will choose afforestation over agricultural production if it maximizes their utility (Phaneuf and Requate 2023). This includes monetary returns and costs as well as non-monetary values included such as private amenity values (Hartman, 1976, Lautrup et al., 2021). In the following, we will depict the decision for an individual landowner.

Assuming an infinite time horizon, and letting the term capital value capture both monetary and non-monetary utility components, the capital value of agricultural production (NPV_A) for an individual landowner is assumed to be the present value of all future net benefits for agricultural (A) land use (NB_A), using a discount rate of r :

$$NPV_A = \frac{NB_A}{r} \quad (1)$$

Similarly, the capital value of afforestation (NPV_F) for the individual landowner can be described as:

$$NPV_F = \sum_{t=0}^T (NB_{F,t1} * (1+r)^{-t}) + \frac{\sum_{t=0}^T ((NB_{F,t2}) * (1+r)^{-t})}{1 - (1+r)^{-T}} \quad (2)$$

Where $NB_{F,t1}$ is net benefits for land-use forest (F) in the first rotation, $NB_{F,t2}$ is the net benefits in the second rotation, t is the time for when the net revenue is occurring, and T is the rotation length. Here we assume that the net benefits over rotations differ between the first and the second rotation as growth conditions and establishment costs differ between afforestation on agricultural land and planting trees in on existing forest land. Furthermore, the specification allows for the forest to enter into a continuous cover management regime.

In a world without uncertainty, utility maximizing landowners will choose the land-use that maximizes their utility and either establish the forest (right away) or continue with agricultural production. As agriculture is the current land-use for our respondents we must therefore assume NPV_A to be higher than NPV_F . If the government wants to incentivize afforestation, they can provide a subsidy $S \geq (NPV_A - NPV_F)$, to get the utility maximizing landowner to change land-use from agriculture to forestry.

However, in the real world, political goals may change, or governments may realize that the current subsidy level is not sufficient to meet the goals that have been set. Hence, the subsidy rate for afforestation may change. If the landowner realizes this, the implication is that an option to *either* wait and see whether the subsidy changes occurs and thus postpone the decision to the future, *or* to make the decision now. Let S_1 denote the subsidy rate today and S_2 the subsidy rate in the next period. In our case, we assume this next period to be five years after present. For simplicity, we look at a two-period example in this theoretical setup. Without lack of generalization, it could easily be expanded to include more periods.

In period 2, the decision problem can be denoted as:

$$V_2 = \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} NPV_A \\ NPV_F + S_2 \end{array} \right\} \quad (3)$$

Where V_2 is the value gained from the choice outcome of the decision problem in period 2.

The decision problem in period 1 can be written as:

$$V_1 = \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} NPV_A, \\ NPV_F + S_1, \\ NB_A + \partial(E(V_2)) \end{array} \right\} \quad (4)$$

Where V_1 is the value gained from the choice outcome of the decision problem in period 1 and $E(V_2)$ is the expected value of the decision problem in period 2, and ∂ is the discount factor.

Let's for simplicity assume that

$$S_2 = S_1 + \left\{ \begin{array}{l} p_u \Delta S \\ p_e 0 \\ -p_d \Delta S \end{array} \right\} \quad (5)$$

Where p_u and p_d are the probabilities that increase or decrease S by ΔS and p_e is the probability that it stays the same. Hence,

$$E(V_2) = \begin{array}{l} p_u(NPV_F + S_1 + \Delta S) + \\ p_e(NPV_F + S_1) + \\ p_d \max(NPV_F + S_1 - \Delta S; NPV_A) \end{array} \quad (6)$$

If $NPV_A > NPV_F + S_1$, afforestation will not take place in period 1. Only if a realized ΔS is large enough to make $NPV_A < NPV_F + S_2$, will afforestation take place in period 2. If, on the other hand $NPV_A < NPV_F + S_1$, afforestation will only take place in period 1 if

$$NPV_F + S_1 > NB_A + \partial E(V_2) \quad (7)$$

This is due to the option value. In our empirical context, we do not know any of the NPVs, nor the probabilities. The probabilities are subjective beliefs of the landowner. We only estimate the S that will make the landowner willing to switch. In split 3, we eliminate the option value caused by policy uncertainty by paying out ΔS as a compensation in case of an increase being realized. Therefore, by comparing the required subsidy in split 3 with the required subsidy without this compensation in split 1 and split 2, we have an estimate of the option value. Which of the two splits are then appropriate to compare? A comparison between split 1 and 3 is probably the one reflecting the real decision context best, as no information is given about uncertainty, and the decision will be therefore dependent on whichever insight the landowner has. However, as we are not observing a real decision, but the result of a hypothetical choice, it is likely that they are less well reflected than they would be in a real context. Therefore, in split 2 we remind landowners of the uncertainty, which means that if they were not aware of the symmetric uncertainty before our reminder, we would expect them to have a higher option value when comparing with split 2 than when comparing with split 1. Though, if landowners, before getting informed about the symmetric uncertainty of the change in ΔS , only expected ΔS to increase in the future, they would now be reminded of the probability that it could also decrease, and their option value could be expected to be lower when comparing with split 2 than split one. The option value will in both cases reflect the situation that there is policy uncertainty about future subsidy levels which will be revealed as time passes. It could be expected that there would also be an option value for other uncertain aspects, e.g. concerning the revenue from agriculture. This will not be captured in our estimate, since we only compensate for changes in subsidy levels.

3. Materials

3.1 Data collection

A sample of respondents was randomly drawn from The Danish Agricultural Agency's list of all 29,654 CVR-numbers of landowners who in 2022 received the basic income support for sustainability (EU based subsidy under the CAP). Before randomization, the lists were split in two groups – large landowners with a registered area of or above 50 ha, and small landowners with a registered area of less than 50 ha. 50% of the sample was drawn from each group. The lists of large and small landowners contained 10,564 and

19,090 landowners respectively. A deliberate overrepresentation of the large landowners was chosen to acknowledge that they represent a larger share of the land (the list of large landowners represents around 2 million ha land which in 2022 received the basic income support for sustainability and the list of small landowners represents a little less than 300 000 ha¹). This is important because the national policies are area-based - a target of 250,000 ha of afforestation in Denmark before 2045 (The Danish Government 2024). The data were collected from October to December 2024 as an online questionnaire, using the software Survey-Xact. The questionnaire was distributed to landowners via E-boks, a national electronic mail system, using the central national register of businesses (CVR) where all businesses in acting in Denmark are registered.

A pilot was distributed to 231 respondents. After the pilot survey, minor changes in the follow-up questions and survey restrictions were carried out before distribution to the full sample. For the full sample, 6,000 questionnaires were distributed.

3.2 Survey design

A draft survey was developed based on previous research on landowner motivation for afforestation and forest ownership (Boon, Meilby, and Thorsen 2004; Guyard and Lundhede 2023; Broch and Vedel 2012). Following, feedback was collected from employees at the Danish Agricultural Agency, the Danish Climate Forest Fund, and five different forest consultancy companies, including both large and small companies, resulting in some reformulations to avoid misunderstandings.

The final survey contained three parts. First respondents were asked about their experience with forestry, whether they had previously planted forest, and their reasons for or against previously planting forest, whether they have plans to plant forest, and their reasons. The second part, a choice experiment, included a section with information about the attributes and instructions to the choice experiment. A few questions about property size and knowledge of the Danish climate reporting rules were included in the text to

¹ The area which is reported in the list from the Danish Agricultural Agency of landowners receiving basic income support for sustainability in 2022 and the total agricultural area are not the same, since not all agricultural areas have received subsidy. There will therefore be a difference in the respondents stated agricultural area and the one that registered area in the list from the Danish Agricultural Agency.

ensure that respondents related to the information provided and to ease the cognitive burden of long text pieces. After the choice sets, a line of more general follow-up questions was presented to all respondents. The third part of the survey contained questions about socio-demographic information. The survey was restricted such that respondents could not go back and change or see previous answers, and they could not skip answers.

Each respondent was asked to complete six choice sets, each containing two possible contracts options and one business-as-usual option called *no contract*, as shown in Figure 1. A list of attributes, their levels, and a description are shown in Table 1. The attributes and their levels were chosen based on experience from previous studies (Boon, Meilby, and Thorsen 2004; Guyard and Lundhede 2023; Broch and Vedel 2012) as well as the ongoing suggested policies. Their relevance and formulation were checked in the survey preparation phase (See above). The choice sets were statistically treated as unlabeled choice sets, but to make the design easier to read for the respondent, it was displayed as labeled choice sets, with the provider of the contracts being the label of each choice option.

The second attribute, *Share of active farmland where afforestation takes place*, is shown as percentages of the respondents' active farmland. To make realistic alternatives, the range differed for small and large landowners.

For the pilot study, an orthogonal design was used. Based on the results of an MNL estimation on these data, priors were obtained and used for creating the final design. This choice design was optimized for d-efficiency in Ngene assuming a Multinomial logit model, with 36 choice situations and six blocks. The same design was used for all splits. Table 2 illustrates the 2x3 splits which were made to investigate the hypotheses. The splits are divided into three splits of small landowners and three splits of large landowners, providing different information on uncertainty: Split 1) a neutral scenario: no information about uncertainties of future schemes is provided, Split 2) a policy uncertainty scenario: we highlight that future schemes might offer better or worse payments than the ones available now depending on progress towards the 2030 goal, Split 3) an uncertainty reduction scenario: the same information as in Split 2 is provided, but a premium is introduced where, if they decide to enrol in one of the contracts, any increase in payment levels the next five years will be compensated.

3.3 Data cleaning

19 respondents, who dropped out during the choice experiment and did not complete all six choice sets, were excluded from the dataset.² The total number of responses included in the survey was 834, giving a response rate of 13.4%. Follow-up questions were included after the choice experiment serial non-responses, those who chose ‘no contract’ in all six choice sets, to identify ‘invalid serial non-responses’, respondents who, for different reasons, did not understand the task. This approach is in line with the recent literature on how to design a choice experiment (Mariel et al. 2021b). The total number of serial non-responses was 401, with 143 being ‘invalid serial non-responses’, which were removed from the dataset before modelling the results, yielding a total of 681 valid responses. Invalid serial non-respondents were identified as those giving the reason ‘The task was too difficult to understand’, ‘I did not understand the purpose of the task’, ‘The options were unrealistic’, ‘I need more information, before making a choice about doing afforestation’ and ‘I cannot join into an afforestation scheme, even if I wanted too. (As an example, I cannot get dispensation to do afforestation)’.

4. Methods

4.1 Model estimation

We follow the random utility theory, assuming that an individual will always choose the option that gives them the highest utility. The utility an individual $n = 1, \dots, N$ obtain from an alternative $j = 1, \dots, J$, can be described by U_{nj} . The individual will choose alternative $i \in J$ if and only if $U_{ni} > U_{nj}$. Since the true utility cannot be observed and an estimated utility as an approximation of the true utility is therefore obtained. The function of the estimated utility can be denoted as $V_{nj} = V(x_{nj}, s_{nj}) \forall j$ and holds a set of attributes used for estimation $x_{nj} \forall j$ and some attributes which belongs to the individual s_{nj} . The difference between the true utility U_{nj} and the estimated utility V_{nj} is due to factors that cannot be estimated which can be described as an unobserved error component ϵ_{nj}

² A set of results was estimated including these responses, yielding insignificant differences

between the results with and without the drop-out. The drop-out were therefore excluded to keep allowing for the use of follow-up questions.

making $U_{nj} \neq V_{nj}$. The estimated utility can be denoted $V_{nj} = x_{nj} + \epsilon_{nj}$ (Kenneth E. Train 2003).

One of the most common and widely used models to estimate the probability of an individual choosing an alternative is the multinomial logit (MNL) model (Kenneth E. Train 2003). In the MNL-model, the error term is logistically distributed, and the utility is usually specified to be linear in its parameters. The probability can be given by (McFadden and Train 2000):

$$P_{ni} = \frac{e^{\beta' x_{ni}}}{\sum_j e^{\beta' x_{nj}}} \quad (8)$$

For the standard logit model, $\beta' x_{ni}$ defines the utility of an individual choice, i , including the attributes of the choice x_{ni} and the coefficient β representing the individual preferences. The MNL-model does not allow for heterogeneity in preferences. This can be an issue, when working with landowners where earlier studies have shown large heterogeneity (Swart et al. 2023; Boon, Meilby, and Thorsen 2004). To allow for that, the probability of an individual choosing a specific alternative should be estimated by using the integral of the standard logit probability over a density of parameters (Mariel and Meyerhoff 2018). The mixed logit model (also called random parameter model) follows the logistic probability function, but compared to the MNL-model, the mixed logit model allows for heterogeneity in the estimated parameters, assuming heterogeneity in preferences (Mariel et al., 2021). The probabilities of an individual choosing an alternative under the mixed distribution can be denoted as (Kenneth E. Train 2003);

$$P_{ni} = \int \left(\frac{e^{\beta' x_{ni}}}{\sum_j e^{\beta' x_{nj}}} \right) \phi(\beta|b, W) d\beta, \quad (9)$$

where P_{ni} is the probability that an individual n , choosing a particular alternative i . The probability can be described by the integral of the standard logit probability, which is explained for equation 8. $\phi(\beta|b, W) d\beta$ is the density function with mean b and covariance W .

To convert the parameter estimates from the mixed logit model from probabilities to cost estimates, the probabilities can be estimated as a willingness to pay or in our case, where it is a subsidy which is offered, a willingness to accept compensation (WTA) measure. This measure represents the negative marginal rate of substitution between an attribute and the price parameter. By doing this, potential scale effects between splits will be cancelled out (Hess, Rose, and Hensher 2008). These measure can be directly applied in

a cost benefit analysis and can also inform decision makers by themselves (Mariel et al., 2021). In this paper a mixed logit model was estimated, but rather than deriving WTA ex post, it was estimated direct in willingness to pay space () using the package Apollo 3.5 for R, defining the data as pseudo-panel data and applying heterogeneity across individuals (Hess and Palma 2019; Hess, Rose, and Hensher 2008; Hess et al. 2025).

4.2 Utility specifications

The utility functions used in all three models are defined as:

$$V_0 = ASC_0 \quad (10)$$

$$V_1 = ASC_1 + \beta_S * Subsidy + \beta_P * OtherProvider + \beta_A * Area + \beta_T * TreeSpecies + \beta_U * Untouched + \beta_{CV} * CarbonVoluntaryMarket + \beta_{CP} * CarbonPrivatAccounting + \beta_B * EarlyBonus + \beta_{PP} * PartialPayment + C_large \quad (11)$$

where V_0 is the estimated utility of the “no contract alternative” described by the alternative specific constant ASC_0 , fixed at zero. V_1 is the estimated utility for choosing one of the two proposed contracts for alternative one or two. The estimated β for the attributes are as defined in table 1. C_large is a constant modelled as a dummy variable covering landowners that receive EU farm subsidy. The dummy takes the value 0 if farmers own less than 50 ha and 1 if they own more than 50 ha..

Except for the subsidy parameter, all parameters are estimated to be normally distributed. The subsidy parameter is estimated to be log-normal to avoid arbitrary negative subsidy values. For generating random draws, the Modified Latin Hypercube Sampling (MNHS) was applied, and each of the three models was estimated using 12.000 draws (Hess and Palma 2019).

5. Results

The socio-demographic characteristics of the sample in terms of, sex, age, household income, and location of property are shown in Appendix A. It is seen that the sample consists of around 90% men, 5% women and the rest that either have not answered this question or do not identify with any of these two categories. More than 50% of the sample is above 60 years and the sample is spread on income and location. In 2020 Statistics Denmark published a portrait of the Danish farmer where they defined the population of Danish farmers as consisting of 94% men and with 50% being 55 years or older (Pedersen et al. 2022). Our sample statistics therefore corresponds well with the general

characteristics of the Danish farmers. There were no significant differences between the distributions of socio-demographic characteristics across splits.

Table 3 presents the willingness to accept (WTA) estimates for all three splits, presented in thousand Danish kroner (t. DKK). The estimates with positive numbers indicate an increase in required compensation and negative numbers indicate a decrease in required compensation levels. The alternative specific constants (ASC) are modelled as the general WTA for accepting a contract. The constants for large landowners, are estimated as dummy, i.e. it should be interpreted as a premium that should be added, to find the required compensation to get large landowners to enroll with one hectare of land. The ASC-estimates thereby illustrate the mean required compensation for getting small landowner to enroll with one hectare of land but holds the heterogeneity for all respondents.

The ASCs reflect the required compensation levels for entering a contract with one hectare of land. To reflect the effect of enrollment area size, an area parameter has been estimated called *Area ha*. This reflects the additional compensation landowners require for additional hectares of land. The estimates range from 0.3-1.5 t. DKK across the three splits, meaning that for each additional ha of land that the landowners enroll, the required compensation level increases.

To test the core hypothesis that *Respondents will have a higher willingness to enter a contract if they get compensated for potentially better contracts in the future than if not*, we compare ASC from split 3 against the ASC's from split 1 and 2 with a t-test and find them to be significantly different at a 5% level. Since a significantly lower WTA is found in split three, the hypothesis cannot be rejected.

The underlying hypothesis 1.1 which states that *Respondents' willingness to enter contracts is independent of the information on uncertainty related to future schemes* is tested by comparing the estimated ASC's for split 1 and 2 with a t-test. We find that the ASC's for split 1 and 2 are significantly different at a 5% level. Hence, independence of uncertainty information is rejected.

The difference between large and small owners is assumed to be expressed in a level shift hence large owners interact with ASC, cf. above. As seen in table 3, large landowners have a higher WTA for entering a contract than small landowners. The hypothesis 1.2 that *Landowners willingness to accept for entering an afforestation scheme is affected by their property size* cannot be rejected and a difference between WTA dependent on

property size is found. To find the required compensation for large landowners, the large landowner constant should be added to the ASC. For split one, the ASC is 98 and the large landowner constant is 59. This means that for the small landowners in split one, the required mean compensation for entering with one hectare of land is 98 t. DKK and for a large landowner the required compensation for entering with one hectare of land is 157 t. DKK. For split two and three correspondingly, the mean required compensation levels for small landowners are 72 and 33 t. DKK and 148 and 122 t. DKK for a large landowner. In general, the estimates hold large standard deviations, reflecting large heterogeneity among respondents.

When comparing the required compensation level for large landowners, it is seen that the WTA differs between splits and hence is affected by information and compensation. This means that hypothesis 1.1, investigating the effect of providing information on the WTA, can be rejected for both large and small landowners, and the core hypothesis investigating whether the WTA decreases when compensation is given, cannot be rejected for either large or small landowners. Hence, an information and a compensation effect is found both for small and large landowners.

Looking at the remaining attributes, it is seen from the estimates concerning the use of the carbon sequestered from the afforestation indicate that the ownership and possibility to use or sell the carbon rights from the sequestration may affect WTA. None of the two attributes are significant across all splits, but both estimates are significant across two splits, with a negative estimate indicating a decrease in WTA if the sequestered carbon can be used on the voluntary carbon market or in their own accounting. This is in line with the findings from the follow-up questions, where only 15% of the respondents answered that they did not care what happened with the potential credits from their afforestation, and around 50% of the respondents indicated that they believed that it would be useful for them to be able to use the sequestered carbon in their climate reporting in the future (Ryge et al. 2025).

For the estimate of partial payment, two of the three splits are significant at a 5% level, with a negative estimate, indicating that lowering the uncertainty by securing partial payment if only parts of the establishment are successful can decrease the WTA.

The estimate for requiring the use of natural succession followed by set-aside forest is positive and significant at a 1% level for split one, negative and significant at a 1% level

for split two, and positive and significant at a 10% level for split three. Hence, the information may affect the perception of this management alternative.

Table 4 shows the estimated option values as the difference between split one and three and the difference between split two and three for both small and large landowners. For the small landowners, this option values are obtained by comparing the ASC-estimates across the splits. To find the option value for the large landowners, the comparison across splits are done on the aggregated value of ASC and the premium for large landowners, which in the table 2 corresponds to adding the large landowner constant to the mean ASC. The option values range from 31.5 – 64.5 thousand DKK/ha, indicating that the uncertainty concerning future subsidy levels does increase the WTA for entering a contract, and that this increase in WTA could be avoided by offering landowners some security for future changes.

As mentioned in chapter 2, the two different ways of deriving the option value may reflect differences in the uncertainty perception with and without information about uncertainty for future subsidy levels. It is seen that, especially for the small landowners, the option value derived from split two compared to split three is much lower than the option value derived from split one and three, without information.

Comparing the option values between the large and small landowners, it is seen that the small landowners seem to have higher option values than the large landowners. Compared with the ASC estimates and the combined estimates of ASC and the large landowner constant, it is also seen that the option values take up a larger share of the general WTA for entering a contract for small landowners than for large landowners.

6. Discussion

This paper investigates landowners' demand for compensation for engaging in afforestation schemes and contributes to the limited literature exploring option values caused by uncertainty of future policies. In addition to estimating option values and comparing the effect of information, the study demonstrates how variations in property sizes affect the demand for compensation.

We estimate mean compensation levels ranging from 33.3 t. DKK to 156.78 t. DKK depending on property size and the existence of policy uncertainty. A recent study from Jørgensen et. al. (2025) estimates the opportunity costs of afforestation on agricultural land in Denmark and find that the farmer's opportunity costs range from 53-62 t. DKK,

depending on the applied discount rate, forest type and soil conditions. Thus our estimates are two to three times larger than these estimated opportunity costs. Only in the case of no policy uncertainty, the required compensation level is below the opportunity costs, and only for small landowners. In theory, we would expect landowners to be indifferent between agriculture or silviculture, if the utility they gain is equal (Phaneuf and Requate 2016). The difference between the opportunity costs and the compensation levels may therefore be due to other factors than pure profit maximization. A number of studies investigates decision making for various agri-environmental schemes and points to other factors which may affect the choice of land use (Castro Campos 2022; Espinosa-Goded, Barreiro-Hurlé, and Ruto 2010; Dessart, Barreiro-Hurlé, and Van Bavel 2019; Lastra-Bravo et al. 2015; Espinosa-Goded, Barreiro-Hurlé, and Dupraz 2013). A study from 2010 using a choice experiment for agri-environmental schemes finds that landowners have a strong preference for keeping the land use that they currently have and where the practice is known (Espinosa-Goded, Barreiro-Hurlé, and Ruto 2010). This was also the case for a study assessing contract design preferences for afforestation schemes in Germany, where Lienhoop & Brouwer (2015) find that half of the respondents that did not want to do afforestation on their land reasoned it with them being farmers and not foresters. Dessart et. al. (2019) investigates behavioral factors influencing sustainable farming practices and find that cognitive factors including the perceived costs and benefits also affects choices. The perceived costs and benefits include option values and are discounted using the farmers' personal discount factor of time. In our study we do not inform farmers about the estimated costs of afforestation. If they are unaware of the real costs this might lead to strategic bias, where the respondents overestimate the compensation in order to be sure that their costs are covered. This is supported by Espinosa-Goded et. al. (2013) who find that lack of know-how can be a barrier for adoption to agri-environmental schemes. Similarly, Lienhoop & Brouwer (2015) find that providing technical forest management advice can lower the WTA. In our study we also see that the uncertainty about future options affects the mean required compensation level which we translate into estimated option values.

By conducting a choice experiment with three different splits, we have been able to estimate option values, presented in table 3. These option values suggest that we may see landowners who are “sitting on the fence” i.e. being reluctant to join into afforestation schemes, due to uncertainty about future schemes and options. When comparing the

estimated option values with the mean WTA, the option values accounts for 20-60% of the mean WTA. As explained in the introduction the difference between the option values may reflect that landowners without information, have an asymmetric uncertainty expectation, only expecting the subsidy levels to go up, and thereby having a higher option value, than when they are reminded of the uncertainty being symmetric, with the possibility that the subsidy can both go up and down. The respondents have not been asked about their expectations for future subsidy changes, and this is therefore only speculation. In terms of policy implications this means that giving some sort of security to the landowners about future changes could potentially decrease the required subsidies needed to get landowners to join, and especially when focusing on small landowners.

The results concerning the option value contribute to a discussion of uncertainty and permanence connected to enrollment in environmental schemes. The effect of uncertainty, contract length, permanence and irreversibility has been demonstrated in previous literature (Raina et al. 2021; Hasler et al. 2019; Greiner 2016; Lienhoop and Brouwer 2015; Broch and Vedel 2012). Broch & Vedel (2012) and Hasler et. al. (2019) estimates the value of cancelling a contract for afforestation and agri-environmental schemes. Both studies find that having this regret option lowers the WTA. Several studies find that the duration of the contract influences the WTA, with increasing WTA for increasing duration length for agri-environmental and biodiversity conservation schemes (Ruto and Garrod 2009; Greiner 2016; Raina et al. 2021; Lienhoop and Brouwer 2015). Hence, we would assume that afforestation schemes, which by definition are permanent, will be met by reluctance which again would lead to high option values and high compensation requirements. As mentioned in chapter 2, the option value only reflects the value of certainty about future subsidy levels, not other forms of uncertainty. If these factors had also been included, it is likely that the full option value would be higher. This could explain some of the differences between the opportunity costs and the compensation requirements where policy uncertainty is removed.

The results show that large and small landowners have different mean WTA for entering an afforestation scheme. Large landowners require higher compensation to join with one ha of land than small landowners. In a similar Danish study from 2012, Broch & Vedel find no difference in preferences between large and small landowners. A recent study, using a hedonic house price method to investigate landowners' value of private amenities from forest, shows that small landowners have higher amenity values from forest than

large landowners (Lautrup et al. 2023). The higher amenity values for small landowners could support the findings that the small landowners require a lower compensation to enroll in an afforestation scheme, since they get a higher utility from the related amenity values of afforestation than large landowners. Furthermore, larger farms are often managed more intensively. A study from 2014 analyzing farmers willingness to accept “Greening” in Germany points to the level of intensification as a factor that can be a barrier for some farmers to change to more sustainable land uses (Latacz-Lohmann et al., 2014). Similar barriers may be present in our case. In a follow-up question, 46% of the ones not interested in afforestation motivated this with needing the land for agriculture (Ryge et al. 2025). Our results show that for both large and small landowners, the more land that needs to be enrolled in a contract, the higher the WTA per ha. The results show a size premium of 300-1,450 DKK pr. ha which should be added to the mean compensations levels per additional ha that the landowners enroll. This is in line with what other studies find for enrollment in agri-environmental schemes (Raina et al. 2021; Lienhoop and Brouwer 2015). To also contribute to biodiversity conservation goals, it is a policy ambition in this case to get larger coherent nature and forest areas, our study shows that this may require higher compensation levels.

We find large heterogeneity in preferences. This is in line with earlier findings from choice experiment studies on farmers’ preferences for agri-environmental schemes (Swart et al. 2023; Boon, Meilby, and Thorsen 2004; Espinosa-Goded, Barreiro-Hurlé, and Ruto 2010; Christensen et al. 2011; Beharry-Borg et al. 2013; Ruto and Garrod 2009). This implies that differentiating subsidy levels between landowners or applying reverse auctions can be significantly more cost-effective than uniform flat rate subsidies.

One potential caveat in our study is the relatively low number of respondents. In the design, the total pool of respondents is divided into three splits, with each split and each model holding a small number of respondents (212-250) with a high heterogeneity in preferences. This may explain why some of the attributes were not significant, despite our a priori expectations. This is the case for the attribute natural succession followed by set-aside, where both negative and positive parameter estimates are observed between the splits and where some were significant and others not. This can also be a consequence of the choice cards being relatively complex. However, complexity was a particular focus in the survey design phase, and in that process, it was not judged too difficult. To make sure that all respondents had the same prior knowledge and understanding of the meaning

of the attributes, all attributes were explained in detail before the choice sets were presented. But the degree to which they spend enough time reading this to capture the content is not investigated. Despite some complexity in the choice sets, the idea of the choice task for the landowners should be easily understood, as it resembles decisions the landowners are faced with in real life – which land use to choose. This may also reflect that the core attributes of participation (ASC), area and price are all significant and robust across model specifications.

Some aspects of selection bias may be present, since answering the survey was voluntary and it could therefore be expected that only landowners interested in afforestation would answer. However, 59% of the respondents stated that they were not interested in planting forest on their land (Ryge et al. 2025). This shows that our sample does include a substantial amount of respondents who a priori are not particularly interested in the topic. Finally, the results are prone to hypothetical bias. This is a consequence of using stated preferences. In the design of the survey, we have tried to minimize it, by using realistic choice alternatives that assembles the real options that the landowners are facing, but it is likely that some strategic answers might still be in play. Shortly after the data collection, payment ranges of 92 t.DKK per hectare were announced as political suggestions from the government based on a report published about half a year before the data collection (Svarer et al. 2024). It is likely that landowners have had a starting point bias in that range.

7. Concluding remarks

The study has investigated subsidy requirements for Danish landowners to do afforestation. Using a discrete choice experiment, we find subsidy rates well above the opportunity costs. By the study design, we can tease out option values related to policy uncertainty of the future subsidy rates. It is likely that option values related to other uncertainty aspects can also play a role in explaining the difference to opportunity costs. Our study suggests a specific uncertainty removing mechanism, guaranteeing landowners increases in compensation if future compensations for the same land-use change increases. This can reduce WTA significantly and may ensure larger participation. This seems particularly important in the case study, Denmark, where the ambition is to increase forest cover by 38% in just 20 years, i.e. a large participation is needed.

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Is moved to the title page for review purposes.

Declaration of interest statement

The authors are not themselves landowners and have no conflict of interest.

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Appendix A; Sociodemographic distribution of the sample

	SPLIT 1 No information	SPLIT 2 Information about uncertainty	SPLIT 3 Information and compensation
Sex			
Men	88,8	91,5	92,6
Women	6,0	4,7	4,8
Other	0,4	0,0	0,4
No answer	4,8	3,8	2,2
Age			
20-39 years	2,8	5,2	7,4
40-59 years	37,6	30,7	32,8
60-79 years	53,2	57,5	52,8
80+ years	6,4	5,7	6,6
No answer	0,0	0,9	0,4
Household income			
0-24,9 t DKK	9,6	6,1	7,4
25-49,9 t DKK	19,6	25,0	20,1
50-69,9 t DKK	18,0	17,9	21,9
70-89,9 t DKK	14,0	11,3	12,7
90-99,9 tDKK	3,6	5,2	2,6
More then 100 tDKK	16,8	15,6	18,3
No answer	18,4	18,9	17,1
Regions			
Hovedstaden	5,6	5,7	7,4
Midtjylland	28,0	26,9	30,1
Nordjylland	15,6	19,8	16,2
Sjælland	18,4	13,7	14,0
Syddanmark	23,6	25,9	27,1
No answer	8,8	8,0	5,2
Responses	250	212	229

Tables

Table 1. Attributes and levels presented in the choice sets. As the opt out is no contract, the attributes have 0 as reference point. * indicates reference levels in the estimation

Attribute	Levels
1. Providers	The Danish Agricultural Agency * The Danish Climate Forest Fund A private fund The municipality
2. Area (as share of active farmland where afforestation takes place) ³	Large landowners (≥ 50 ha): 2%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25% Small landowners (< 50 ha): 10%, 15%, 25%, 35%, 50%, 60%
3. Tree species	Free choice of tree species* At least 75% native tree species
4. Natural succession followed by set aside forest ⁴	No * Yes
5. Carbon market	Enters only in national accounting* Enters in national accounting and can be sold at the voluntary carbon market Enters in the national accounting and can be used for the farm's climate report
6. Early bonus	No * Yes (10,000 DKK if enrolling before a specified date)
7. Partial payment (if the forest is only partially established)	No * Yes
8. Bid sizes (DKK / ha) ⁵	20 000, 35 000, 50 000, 60 000, 80 000, 95 000, 110 000, 125 000

³In the modelling the percentages are converted into hectare by using the stated size of a farm's agricultural land

⁴ In the Danish literature set aside forest are often referred to as untouched forest. Sometimes the term unmanaged is also used. In Danish management practice, it refers to a forest where no harvesting is taking place.

⁵ When the survey was carried out, 1 000 DKK were equivalent to 134 Euro (European Central Bank, 2025).

Table 2. Split design illustrating the 2x3 splits with three different levels of information provided before each choice set. For each of the choice sets there is two identical splits, one for large and one for small landowners.

Split no.	Information provided
1. neutral scenario	Would you do afforestation based on the options provided? Choose one of the schemes shown in the first or second row or no contract, if you do not want to do afforestation with any of the two options.
2. information about uncertainty	If we are not on the right track to reaching the national goals on CO ₂ -emission when we approach 2030, the incitement for the subsidy schemes might change. This can cause the subsidy to either increase or decrease dependent on how the politicians choose to go forward with reaching the goals. Based on this uncertainty, would you do afforestation today based on the options provided? Choose one of the schemes shown in the first or second row or no contract, if you do not want to do afforestation with any of the two options.
3. information about uncertainty and premium	If we are not on the right track to reaching the national goals on CO ₂ -emission when we approach 2030, the incitement for the subsidy schemes might change. This can cause the subsidy to either increase or decrease dependent on how the politicians choose to go forward with reaching the goals. To avoid this uncertainty a premium is guaranteed; if the public subsidy levels for afforestation increase within the next five years, you will be compensated with this premium. Given this information, would you do afforestation today based on the options provided? Choose one of the schemes shown in the first or second row or no contract, if you do not want to do afforestation with any of the two options.

Table 3. Willingness to pay estimates from the three splits. The estimates are presented in t. DKK/ha and the standard errors are for each estimate presented in parentheses to the right of the estimate and the significance identifier.

	SPLIT 1 Neutral scenario	SPLIT 2 Information about uncertainty	SPLIT 3 Information about uncertainty and premium
ASC			
Mean	97.76 *** (4.62)	71.75 *** (-6.82)	33.30 *** (10.02)
SD	132.82 *** (8.90)	207.89 *** (25.39)	166.48 *** (10.58)
Large lanowners			
Constant	59.02 *** (3.96)	76.34 *** (8.97)	83.29 *** (4.71)
Other Providers			
Mean	1.00 (3.06)	-6.82 * (4.06)	7.97 (5.80)
SD	-21.29 *** (1.18)	17.88 *** (2.50)	-32.65 *** (3.09)
75% Native tree species			
Mean	7.79 *** (2.99)	-1.11 (3.90)	8.90 (6.66)
SD	-10.62 *** (1.61)	6.40 ** (3.03)	-19.12 *** (2.69)
Area ha			
Mean	1.05 *** (0.07)	0.31 *** (0.12)	1.45 *** (0.07)
SD	-1.05 *** (0.07)	0.19 *** (0.07)	-1.29 *** (0.06)
Private carbon accounting			
Mean	-3.18 (3.16)	-7.87 * (4.67)	-8.47 *** (1.80)
SD	-19.23 *** (2.08)	-28.83 *** (2.54)	-0.61 (0.67)
Voluntary carbon market			
Mean	-6.03 ** (2.69)	-10.03 ** (4.69)	-4.71 (6.13)
SD	-4.12 *** (1.12)	-0.49 (1.99)	2.45 (6.41)
Early bonus			
Mean	-13.47 *** (2.08)	1.38 (3.15)	-3.95 (2.45)
SD	6.22 *** (0.71)	0.03 (1.57)	-1.22 (1.05)
Natural succession			
Mean	11.59 *** (4.04)	-15.47 *** (4.92)	10.59 * (5.42)
SD	-7.31 *** (1.08)	-16.22 *** (3.69)	19.00 *** (0.47)
Partial payment			
Mean	-5.01 ** (2.24)	-7.81 ** (3.68)	-8.18 (9.73)
SD	2.99 *** (0.86)	0.04 (3.77)	-23.65 *** (2.21)
Subsidy thousand DKK			
Mean	2.50 *** (0.26)	2.78 *** (0.25)	2.16 *** (0.53)
SD	1.40 *** (0.28)	-1.17 *** (0.27)	1.67 *** (0.53)
LL(final)	-784.36	-682.74	-771.42
Adjusted R ²	0.5113	0.4964	0.475
Responses	250	212	229
Zero bidders	40%	37.7%	34%

***, **, and * illustrate parameters that are significantly different from zero at respectively 1, 5, and 10% significance levels

Tabel 4. Option value estimates presented in t. DKK/ha and in share of total WTA.

Option values (t. DKK/ha)	Between split 1 and 3	Between split 2 and 3
Small landowners (<50 ha)	64.5 (66%)	38.4 (54%)
Large landowners (>50 ha)	40.2 (26%)	31.5 (21%)

Figures

Figure 1. One of 36 choice sets which was presented to the respondents. Here translated to English from Danish.

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
Provider of the contract	Climate Forest Fund	Municipality	No contract
Share of active farmland, where afforestation takes place	5%	2%	
Tree species and forest structure	Minimum 75% native tree species	Free choice of tree species	
Natural growth and afterwards untouched forest	-	-	
The CO2-sequestration can be incorporated in	✓ National accounting	✓ National accounting ✓ Voluntary carbon market	
Bonus if enrolling before 2025 (10.000 DKK)	✓	✓	
Partial payment at an incomplete establishment	✓	-	
Subsidy in DKK/ha	20 000	125 000	
Your choice	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Choice set 1/6